

NOTES

Studies on Complexes of Molybdenum(V) with Substituted Oxines

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IN continuation of our investigations¹⁻⁵ on the coordination chemistry of quinquevalent molybdenum, we have isolated and studied some new oxobromo derivatives of molybdenyl cation MoO^{5+} . By reducing MoO_3 with concentrated hydrobromic acid⁶ we have isolated $[\text{5,7-Cl}_2/\text{Br}_2\text{-OxineH}_2]_2\text{MoOBr}_5$, where $\text{5,7-Cl}_2/\text{Br}_2\text{-OxineH} = \text{5,7-dichloro/dibromo-8'-hydroxyquinoline}$. By dehydrohalogenation of the salts through heating the solid in inert atmosphere we have isolated paramagnetic non-electrolytic derivative $\text{MoOBr}_3(\text{5,7-Cl}_2/\text{Br}_2\text{-OxineH})$. Hydrolysis of the salts yielded reduced paramagnetic non-electrolytic solids $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_3\cdot\text{Br}_4(\text{5,7-Cl}_2/\text{Br}_2\text{-OxineH})_2$ and $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4\cdot\text{Br}_2(\text{5,7-Cl}_2/\text{Br}_2\text{-OxineH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$. These compounds have been characterised by analytical and other physico-chemical investigations.

Experimental

All reagents used were of A.R. grade. The ligands were synthesised following the standard procedure⁶. Molybdenum and bromide were estimated gravimetrically as MoO_3 and silver bromide, respectively and nitrogen by Dumas' method.

5,7-Dichloro[dibromo-8-hydroxyquinolinium oxopentabromomolybdate(V)]: MoO_3 (~ 1 g) was reduced⁶ with 9 M HBr and to this solution 5,7-dichloro-8-hydroxyquinoline (15 ml) previously dissolved in minimum quantity of HBr was added with stirring. The mixture was cooled in ice-bath when shining brown crystalline solid separated. The product was filtered through gooch crucible, washed with 9 M hydrobromic acid and dried *in vacuo* over solid KOH (2.5 g). Following the same procedure and using 5,7-dibromo-8-hydroxyquinoline (5.2 g), brown crystalline product (3.2 g), was obtained.

Oxotrisbromobis(5,7-dichloro[dibromo-8-hydroxyquinoline)molybdenum(V)]: The paramagnetic non-electrolytic complexes were obtained by heating the salts (0.95 g) at 140° in a glass tube furnace in an inert atmosphere for 13 h, till the evolution of hydrogen bromide gas completely ceased. Yields were 0.8 and 0.78 g with chloro- and bromo-ligands, respectively.

μ -Oxobis(oxodibromo-5,7-dichloro)dibromo-8-hydroxyquinolinemolybdenum(V): The original salt ($\sim 1.2/1.5$ g) with chloro- and bromo-substituted ligands was refluxed with dehydrated ethanol (10 ml) for 2 h, when a deep wine-red solution formed, which on cooling yielded brownish black precipitate. The products were filtered, washed with dehydrated ethanol and dried *in vacuo*. Yields were 0.89 and 0.91 g with chloro- and bromo-ligands, respectively.

Di- μ -oxobis(bromoquo-5,7-dichloro)dibromo-8-hydroxyquinolinemolybdenum(V): The salts (~ 1.0 g) were gently boiled with water (10 ml) for 5 min. The deep brownish black products so formed were filtered, washed with cold water and dried *in vacuo*. Yields were 0.70 and 0.52 g with chloro- and bromo-ligands, respectively.

The analytical and magnetic data of all the complexes are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The conductivity of the two salt type complexes was measured in DMF and those of the two monoxo paramagnetic complexes in acetonitrile medium using 'Dip' type cell. The molar conductance value for the first two complexes is $135 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2$, which is compatible with 2:1 electrolyte, and for the non-electrolytes, *i.e.* $\text{MoOBr}_3(\text{5,7-Cl}_2/\text{Br}_2\text{-OxineH})_2$. The values are 2.6 and $2.1 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2$, respectively.

Magnetic susceptibility of the compounds was measured on Gouy balance at room temperature and magnetic moment values were calculated after necessary diamagnetic correction using the expression $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 2.84 (\chi'_M \times T)^{1/2}$ (where χ'_M = corrected molar susceptibility). The values for two salts and their corresponding monoxo non-electrolytic species are found to be in the range 1.52-1.77 B.M. which are consistent with d^1 configuration of Mo. However, the moments for oxobridged species vary from 0.28 to 0.88 B.M. which are much less than spin-only value due to Mo-Mo interaction⁸.

The ir spectra of the complexes exhibit a very strong absorption at $930\text{-}995 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which may be attributed to the vibration of the symmetric stretching mode of the terminal $\text{Mo}=\text{O}$ bond⁹. The bands in the region $760\text{-}810 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ are assignable¹⁰ to $\nu_{\text{Mo}-\text{O}-\text{Mo}}$. The electronic spectra of the complexes were recorded in a Hilger UVISPEK. The spectra of the two salts were measured in DMF solution while for the others, the reflectance spectra were taken in paraffin base. The MoOBr_3 ion may be assumed to have a tetragonal structure with a short Mo-O bond having C_{4v} symmetry¹¹. The expected transitions with identical scheme agree very closely

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND MAGNETIC DATA OF COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Compd.	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			μ_{eff} B.M.
			Mo	Br	N	
1.	(5,7-Cl ₂ -OxineH ₂) ₂ MoOBr ₅	Brown (crystal)	10.19 (10.72)	42.46 (32.43)	3.0 (2.8)	1.61
2.	(5,7-Br ₂ -OxineH ₂) ₂ MoOBr ₅	Brown (crystal)	8.57 (8.37)	35.70 (36.48)	2.5 (2.7)	1.79
3.	MoOBr ₅ (5,7-Cl ₂ -OxineH) ₂	Brown-black (powder)	12.30 (12.00)	30.76 (30.50)	3.58 (3.70)	1.52
4.	MoOBr ₅ (5,7-Br ₂ -OxineH) ₂	Brown-black (powder)	10.02 (9.80)	25.05 (24.60)	2.92 (2.78)	1.77
5.	Mo ₂ O ₄ Br ₄ (5,7-Cl ₂ -OxineH) ₂	Brown-black (powder)	19.43 (19.39)	32.38 (32.21)	2.88 (2.70)	0.49
6.	Mo ₂ O ₄ Br ₄ (5,7-Br ₂ -OxineH) ₂	Brown-black (powder)	16.46 (16.89)	27.44 (27.85)	2.40 (2.20)	0.28
7.	Mo ₂ O ₄ Br ₄ (5,7-Cl ₂ -OxineH) ₂ ·(H ₂ O) ₂	Brown-black (powder)	21.81 (22.06)	19.18 (18.59)	3.18 (3.12)	0.78
8.	Mo ₂ O ₄ Br ₄ (5,7-Br ₂ -OxineH) ₂ ·(H ₂ O) ₂	Brown-black (powder)	18.14 (18.21)	15.12 (15.01)	2.64 (2.70)	0.88

with the experimental results. The two salts, 5,7-dichloro- and 4,7-dibromo-8-hydroxyquinolinium oxopentabromomolybdate(V) show two crystal field transitions¹¹ ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2E(I)$ and ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_1$ around 14000 and 20000 cm^{-1} and three charge transfer transitions ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2E(II)$, ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_2(I)$ and ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_2$ (II) around 25000, 30000 and 37000 cm^{-1} , respectively. About the monomeric complexes *viz.* MoOBr₅-(5,7-Cl₂-OxineH)₂ and MoOBr₅(5,7-Br₂-OxineH)₂, the molecular orbital picture is expected to be different. In this case the number of symmetry elements is expected to be less than that in the case of MoOBr₅²⁻ ion which belongs to C_{4v} point group. But the other distortions from octahedral structure compared to the distortion caused by Mo-O interaction, are expected to be moderate. In this case, there will be a considerable π -interaction with the filled π -orbitals of the ligand and the metal σ -orbitals, as a result the first crystal field transition appears at a lower frequency range around 13000 cm^{-1} than the parent salt. The second crystal field transition appears around 17500 cm^{-1} , and the third one, L→Mo charge transfer around 24000 cm^{-1} . About the dimeric complexes containing Mo₂O₄⁴⁺ and Mo₂O₄²⁺ moiety, tentative assignments of the spectra have been made. No definite conclusion can be drawn because, due to the presence of oxobridge, the identity of the original [MoOBr₅]²⁻ is somewhat lost and so also the molecular orbital picture. However, it has been observed that the first crystal field transition appears around 13600 cm^{-1} , and L→Mo charge transfer band has experienced a red shift and appears around 19000-22800 cm^{-1} in comparison to 24400 cm^{-1} in case of the corresponding mono-meric compound. A similar observation has been made by Mitchell¹². This is presumably due to the fact that in these cases bromine has been replaced by oxygen, a ligand forming stronger bond with metal and thereby destabilising the Mo-L bond to a small extent.

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Azo Complexes. Complexes of Alkali Metal Salts of some Organic Acids with *o*-Nitrobenzene-azo-2-naphthol and *o*-Chlorobenzene-azo-2-naphthol

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In our previous work¹ we have reported the formation of alkali metal adducts with azo ligands, containing electron pushing groups at *o*- and *o'*-positions to the azo group. Now we are reporting the alkali metal adducts formed with ligands which contain electron withdrawing groups at *o*-position to the azo group. We have synthesised the adducts of alkali metal salts of different organic acids with azo ligands NO₂-BAN and Cl-BAN, of the general formulae ML.NO₂-BAN and ML.Cl-BAN, respectively, where M=Li, Na and K; L=deprotonated organic acids; NO₂-BAN=*o*-nitrobenzene-azo-2-naphthol and Cl-BAN=*o*-chlorobenzene-azo-2-naphthol. Analytical data showed that one molecule